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THE WAYS OF LEARNING PHRASEOLOGIZMS WITH LINGUISTIC COMPONENTS EXPRESSING CULTURAL MEANING IN TEACHING PROCESS

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Annotation: Phraseological unity can come across sentence boundaries and even large parts of the text, specific sources of interdependence and associative connections of figurative and direct information. The linguistic nature of the phraseological unit has been comprehensively studied today. Indeed, knowledge of idioms is an important indicator of target language proficiency. Teaching and learning phrasal verbs helps to reveal the conative processes of the mind in creative thinking. At the same time, it helps to develop other language skills: speaking, reading, etc. Development in lexical, lexical and stylistic awareness can lead to the development of awareness, which includes the perception and development of changes in basic form and meaning. The purpose of this scientific article is to reveal phraseological unity, associative connections and stylistic projects, linguistic cohesion in the text and new meaning in the context through the essence of teaching phraseology.

Key words- phraseological unit, idiomatic expressions, linguistic, component, cognitive, proficiency, language skills, stylistic awareness, creative thinking, didactics.

Introduction

Studying English phraseological units with expressing units and watching English commercials have much in common which makes the choice of this type of authentic video justified and efficient. Having analyzed a number of manuals that give direct recommendations on teaching English via authentic video materials, we can draw that idiomatic language, due to its popularity in everyday use and its figurative meaning causing certain difficulties to learners, is a type of vocabulary which is much easier to comprehend through visual aids. Moreover in the former case, TV commercials are supposed to be visual additional material to a vocabulary section of many textbooks that suggest studying idioms grouped by some particular principle (e.g. expressions with money, penny, cash, coin, shilling, expressions with the verbs make, spend, turn and etc.).

Methodology

Visual images of such idioms as time is money, penny pig and many others help to memorize figurative language and to state the cultural differences (and similarities) with the native language as far as a certain phraseological units is concerned. For example, the meaning of an idiom lost money on the deal can be easily understood without any translation into a native language. Additionally this kind of teaching technique could help English language teachers make studying phraseological units more effective and exciting; we need to turn to the types of activities foreign language teachers use in a classroom. Methods and ways of applying phraseological units in teaching process are widely clarified in the handouts from methodical ways of teaching English as a foreign language. But every teacher who conducts the lesson and wants his lessons to be more useful and affective creates ways of making his classes interesting. It depends on the imagination and creativeness of the teacher.

Data collection and Analysis

The whole range of techniques varies from comprehension exercises to creative writing tasks. The most general examples available to students of various levels are the following:

- Watching a suggested TV commercial and writing down an idiom/idioms used.
- though very common, enables the listeners both to memorize the idiom and to enjoy the process of watching a funny and entertaining advertisement.
- Creating TV commercials on the basis of a particular phraseological units/group of idioms.

A list of phraseological units studied separately or in groups can be suggested by the teacher or arranged by students themselves. This type of work proves to be really inspiring as an out-of-class or homework activity (creating personal advertisements and sharing them with other students in the class). There are plenty of ways of making the teaching process more interesting and affective by using phraseological units. The teacher may explain the idiom first and then may give the definition orally and ask the students to make up examples one by one. The next way may be like this: the teacher may tell the idiom and give just the example and the students should give the definition

it is that what today's up-to-date interactive methods requires us to accomplish. Another one is the students will be arranged into small groups and are supposed to make up short stories according to the phraseological units given by their teacher for example, money has no smell but should not tell the idiom which is supposed to be used in the story. The next group should find the name of the phraseological units. The next activity goes on like following: the teacher hands in the written task which has multiple choice tests belonging to the idioms or phraseological units that should be learned. As a consequence by choosing an appropriate materials for implementing different activities in teaching phraseological units are considerable too important. Teaching materials, part of the five needed components of language instruction (students, a teacher, materials, teaching methods, and evaluation), is a general term to refer to „anything which is used by teachers or learners to facilitate the learning of a language“ [Tomlinson, 1998.]. Teaching materials are of great importance for their guidance in any instructional circumstance. Brown [1995:139] mentions that they provide a detailed description of teaching techniques, methods and the tasks designed for a learner's classroom activities.

Result and discussion

There are many types of teaching materials including paper-based (textbooks), electronic (corpus, computer software), and audio-visual (video, television programs, audio tapes, visual aids). All of them can be used by the teacher but we have a close look at the relationship between textbooks and their content in terms of phraseology. Teaching materials are the basis of language input the learner is exposed to and practice in the classroom [Richards, 2001.]. They are important for the learning of language phraseology and may lead to success or failure to reach the competence aims. As the result of methodical interpretation of visual aids and other form of activities are developed considering specific goals in mind, linguistic and culture oriented peculiarities of the film and its thematic range. The exercises are directed at removing language difficulties, understanding the content of the episode for viewing, disclosure and discussion of the film, explanation of the realities of other cultures. These tasks can be divided into three groups:

- pre-viewing activities,

- first viewing activities and
- comprehension activities.

However, one should not perceive this classification as a mechanical one, because it takes into account not only the time for doing an exercise, but also the type, form and nature of the task defined and limited by this time. The use of audio-visual aids in learning phraseological units with expressing currency units by learners gives an opportunity to implement fully and consistently one of the principles of didactics - visibility. It helps to facilitate the understanding of language units under study, to use analytical skills of students as much as possible, to mobilize their internal resources, to increase the interest to the lessons. In such way it is facilitated the comprehension of foreign language speech and the construction of the statements, as the picture in the frame recreates the situation of communication and the student tries to "see", "to read" situational cues and use them as if a prepared or unprepared statement English language phraseological units using audio-visual aids involves the equipment of methodological apparatus of the pedagogical system in question, the didactic interpretation of authentic viewing episodes as well as the programming of certain training actions, aimed at mastering phraseological units with components currency units by the learners, the development of necessary speaking skills, the formation of a foreign language competence. For all that we should consider not only the native language of students, but the specifics of national culture, educational traditions, which aim to increase the effectiveness of linguo-educational process.

Conclusion

Since learning a foreign language requires both students and teachers to be creative, the latter should be motivated to apply various modern techniques of teaching English phraseology with component expressing currency units (including idioms, proverbs and sayings). While watching authentic video materials, memorizing and playing back or learning idioms and proverbs which can be organizing through various vocabulary-based activities with textbooks is useful and also taking into consideration that although listening and pronouncing are separate skills, the majority of language skills are not and should not be taught separately. Speaking activities, discussion or pair-work are challenging and hugely motivating, and a focus on phraseology makes

the language natural and authentic. All in all, the above-mentioned activities help to overcome some linguistic challenges caused by studying idiomatic expressions, proverbs and sayings, and give a perfect example of how culture infuses a language.

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